
GOLDBACH APPROACH

A POSSIBLE FORMULA FOR CALCULATING BINARY PRIME PARTITIONS OF EVEN NUMBERS.

A PREPRINT

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ABSTRACT

"A mathematician, like a painter or a poet, is a pattern maker. If his patterns are more permanent than theirs, it is because they are made with ideas."

G. H. Hardy

Goldbach conjecture is one of the most famous open problems of mathematics, but its fame is justified by the time that this problem has been unproven and the long list of people who contribute one more piece to this puzzle, which is why this conjecture has two problems, the obvious level of difficulty, and the second is to be able to separate from all the ideas the right ones to be able to give a solution.

Introduction

Goldbach conjecture states that every even number $2n \geq 4$ is the product of the sum of two primes P . This hypothesis comes from the very observation of a phenomenon that apparently repeats itself in a constant and unstoppable way through all even numbers, leading us to think that prime numbers are the building blocks with which all integers can be constructed. The aim of this article is to try to give that behavior a formula, if the even numbers are made of prime numbers, just as there are partitions of any integer, the breakthrough in this area of partitions is given by Ramanujan[3].

1 AXIOMS

We will build the basis of the conjecture from its basic axioms.

- 1 There is a type of number belonging to the \mathbb{R} that can only be divided by 1 and themselves, this set of numbers we will call them prime numbers \mathbb{P} .
- 2 Prime numbers P are infinite.

These axioms were demonstrated by Euclid in his famous work "The Elements" and from these two axioms, one that indicates the existence of these elements and the other that indicates that they are infinite, we can begin to deduce what these truths imply.

1.1 deductions

From the second Axiom, we can deduce that if there are infinitely many primes then there are infinitely many pairs that are of the form $2P$.

We will call this set of numbers $\{\varnothing\}$

Then for these numbers Goldbach conjecture is valid, so the even numbers that do not fall into this set is where the difficulty of this problem lies.

We will call this set of numbers $\{h\}$ and they have the characteristic of being of the form $2n - P = P'$ where $P \neq P'$. Jason R. South (2022)[5] makes an algebraic approach to the Goldbach conjecture where he also comes to use these same deductions.

South makes an approach to come up with the description that if there were a number that could be a counterexample of the conjecture it could not exist because it would be impossible to construct by the Fundamental Theorem of Algebra.

2 Bertrand-Chebyshev Theorem

Bertrand postulate states that there exists at least one prime number between any integer and its double.

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{R} \exists P / n < P < 2n.$$

This theorem was conjectured by Joseph Bertrand and proved by Chebyshev, and is named the Bertrand-Chebyshev theorem.

This extensively studied theorem [1] is in our opinion a key piece for the construction of a possible proof since it shows us that it is possible to obtain coordinates where there must always be at least one prime.

This proof is what we will use to construct a set construction method that progressively builds the even numbers for which the conjecture wants to prove.

2.1 deductions

From this theorem we can deduce simple things that directly imply a continuity in Goldbach Conjecture since for this type of conjecture the way to prove it false is to find a counter example, the following deductions are a clue of how such a number would break the conjecture.

- 1 Between a prime and its double, there is at least one prime number.

$$\forall P \in \mathbb{R} \exists P' / P < P' < 2P.$$

This is the set of infinite numbers that we have already mentioned and that we call $\{\varphi\}$

- 2 If Goldbach conjecture is true, the even numbers that are not of the form $2P$, between P and $2P$, can be constructed with all the primes that exist in that set.

This set of pairs that do not belong to the set $\{\varphi\}$, because they are not of the form $2P$ belong to the set $\{h\}$.

- 3 If Goldbach conjecture is true then all even numbers are the union of the set $\{\varphi\}$ with the set $\{h\}$, and if it is false it would be an even number that does not exist in that set.

$$\{2n_p\} = \{\varphi\} \cup \{h\}$$

From these deductions we can try to construct a method that fits them.

3 Building even numbers

With the sets we have from the deductions we will create a series of steps to see if they correspond to what is described.

Step 1: we take the first prime number and multiply it by two.

$$2 * 2 = 4$$

obviously this number belongs to the set $\{\varphi\}$

Step 2: we take the interval between P and $2P$ and write down in a table to which each element we are looking for belongs:

prime numbers in the interval
 even numbers $2P$
 even numbers other than $2P$

Elements in the range of 2 to 4 = $\{2n_1\}$

P	2P	H
2	4	
3		

Step 3: We take the largest prime of the interval, in this case 3, and multiply it by 2.

$$3 * 2 = 6$$

we build the table again

Elements in the range of 3 to 6 = $\{2n_2\}$

P	2P	H
3	4	
5	6	

Step 4: We repeat the process until we find even numbers that are not 2P.

$$5 * 2 = 10$$

Elements in the range of 5 to 10 = $\{2n_3\}$

P	2P	H
5	10	8
7		

Step 5: When we finally find a number in row H, which means that it is not a 2P number, with the primes within the previous sets we can add them together to arrive at this number H.

$$5 + 3 = 8$$

Is this process infinite? If not, the conjecture would be completely false, since at some point the collection of primes that we accumulate for a pair in a binary sum would not be enough to give it as a result.

at that moment we could stop constructing sets but so far no counter example has been found.

This means that if you do not stop the prime numbers generate a continuity in the set $2n$ which is nothing more than the union of all the micro sets of the intervals generated using the theorem 2.

4 Prime binary partitions

If you continue the process long enough you will realize that there are even numbers 2P that also exist in the set H.

We can define the prime partition of an even number as the number of times that two primes added together give that number, this is because Goldbach Conjecture is also known as Goldbach Binomial Conjecture, there is also a devil's conjecture that claims to have been solved by Helfgott H. (2013)[4].

let's make a small example with the number 26:

$$\begin{array}{r} 23 + 3 \\ 19 + 7 \\ 13 + 13 \end{array}$$

as we can see 26 is a pair that belongs to both sets and it also has 3 binary prime partitions, then let's call the binary prime partitions as π_{pb} .

Then the π_{pb} function of the number 26 would be equal to 3.

$$\pi_{pb}(26) = 3$$

4.1 Examples

$$\pi_{pb}(100) = 6$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 97 + 3 \\ 89 + 11 \\ 83 + 17 \\ 71 + 29 \\ 59 + 41 \\ 47 + 53 \end{array}$$

$$\pi_{pb}(108) = 7$$

103 + 5
 101 + 7
 97 + 11
 89 + 19
 79 + 29
 71 + 37
 61 + 47

$$\pi_{pb}(316) = 9$$

313 + 3
 311 + 5
 293 + 23
 263 + 53
 257 + 59
 233 + 83
 227 + 89
 179 + 137
 167 + 149

As we can see, as the value of the even numbers increases, even if only slightly, there seems to be an increase in their prime partitions.

If Goldbach conjecture is false, then there exists an even number that has no prime partition.

5 Function of approximation to the prime partitions

The following function is an approximation, it does not give the exact number of raw partitions.

Assuming that Goldbach conjecture is true and that every even number $2n \geq 4$ has prime partitions, then it is related to the number of prime numbers less than that pair, so this function would be related to the prime counter function $\pi(n)$.

$$\pi_{pb} \approx \log(2n) * \ln(\pi) \tag{1}$$

Where $\pi(n)$ is the counter function.

As this function depends on another function that is not yet complete, only the value of π is known from known data, we can take it as a postulate or an approach to calculate such partitions if it is correct.

5.1 examples

Let's take the numbers from the previous example 4.1 that we already know their partitions and see how close it is to the prime partitions of those numbers:

- $2n = 100, \pi(100) = 25, \pi_{pb}(100) = 6$

$$\pi_{pb}(100) \approx \log(100) * \ln(25) = 6,43775165$$

- $2n = 108, \pi(108) = 27, \pi_{pb}(108) = 7$

$$\pi_{pb}(108) \approx \log(108) * \ln(27) = 6,701832978$$

- $2n = 316, \pi(316) = 65, \pi_{pb}(316) = 9$

$$\pi_{pb}(316) \approx \log(316) * \ln(65) = 10,43466194$$

the margin of deviation of the result is not so far from the real value.

6 relation of $\pi(n)$ vs $\pi_{pb}(2n)$

The relationship between the number of primes less than an even number, according to the function we saw earlier, shows that there is apparently a relationship between the even numbers and the density of primes less than these numbers.

there is a lot written about this, and the idea is to get an algorithm that would be essential for number theory, this algorithm that counts the number of prime numbers of a given quantity [2], Carl Friedrich Gauss was the first to give an approximation to such a function.

$$\frac{n}{\ln n} \approx \pi(n) \tag{2}$$

Later Legendre, a great mathematician who contributed to many areas of mathematics and number theory, leaves us another approach to the function.

$$\frac{n}{\ln n - 1.08366} \approx \pi(n) \tag{3}$$

For the purposes of this article I developed a prime counter function with a smaller margin of error than the previous ones for a range from 1 to 100

in the formula ($\pi = 3, 141\dots$) does refer to the number and not to the function.

$$\frac{n}{\ln n} + e^{\log(n)} - \pi \approx \pi(n) \tag{4}$$

For a range of 1 to 100 this formula seems to be the closest approximation to the real values of the pi function.

6.1 Graphical comparisons

the first comparison is between the Gaussian formula 2 and the π_{pb} 1 function.

Figure 1: π_1 vs π_{pb1}

The second comparison is Legendre's formula 3 with the formula of the prime partitions 1

Figure 2: π_2 vs π_{pb2}

The third comparison is the proposed formula 4 with the prime partition formula 1.

Figure 3: π_3 vs π_{pb3}

As can be seen, it seems that the function π_{pb} fits very well to the $\pi(n)$ functions previously shown since its value does not vary much with the values of these functions.

In the following figure 4 we can see how the three partition functions of each of the formulas intersect, they are joined to such an extent that it is impossible to differentiate which is which.

Figure 4: $\pi_{pb1}, \pi_{pb2}, \pi_{pb3}$

All these images were created in GeoGebra, the link to see the functions is the following one: <https://www.geogebra.org/calculator/umnxdzeu>

7 Conclusions

To conclude this article by analyzing all the above, we can conclude that if there is an even number that disproves the conjecture, it would have the following characteristics:

- Cannot have prime partitions
- cannot belong to any of the aforementioned groups since it cannot be built.
- must be so exaggeratedly large that the last prime that appeared before the pair is at a very considerable distance, enough to make the conjecture false.

By the theorem 2 we already know that there will always appear at least one prime between a number and its double, this at least generates a limit of appearance, between these spaces that are becoming increasingly larger between the primes, and this tells us that for every even number greater than 4 to divide it in half we will find at least one prime, so there is no even number that is farther away than that, therefore the number of primes will remain and increase as the even numbers appear but none will never be far enough away to not be able to find at least one prime.

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